

UDC 94(7), 93, 94(4), 34(15)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18452843>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4696098>

Konstantin Ashrafyan,

E-mail: kea6465@mail.ru

The Encomienda as a System of Relations between Aborigines and Settlers of the New World through the Prism of the Policy of Christianization and Slavery. 1492-1504.

Abstract. The aim of the study was to investigate the origin of the encomienda in the late 15th and early 16th centuries. In writing the article, primary sources and their translations, as well as scientific articles in various languages, were studied. The methods of content analysis, the comparative-historical method, the chronological method, and the systematic method were applied to identify the cause-and-effect relationships of events occurring in different parts of the world. Conclusions are drawn that the encomienda was introduced due to the need for a legal framework in the relations between Spanish settlers and aborigines in the West Indies, which was already required starting from 1493. By giving the Spanish Crown consent to the transfer of discovered lands in the New World through his Bulls No. 1 – No. 4, the Pope envisioned the expansion of the Christian world through free and Christianized local inhabitants. However, C. Columbus used any actions to obtain profit, up to the slave trade of the local population. The encomienda, introduced in 1503 by Nicolás de Ovando, designated the status of the lands but secured the Indians only as a labor force for the settler-encomenderos. This led to Indian uprisings and alienated Christianization as a goal.

Keywords: Catholic Monarchs, Isabella I of Castile, Ferdinand II of Aragon, encomienda, encomendero, repartimiento, Catholic Kings, Isabella's will of 1504, aboriginal slavery, West Indies, Hispaniola, Christopher Columbus, Alexander VI, slavery, Bull No. 1 *Breve Inter caetera*, Bull No. 2 *minor Inter caetera*, Bull No. 3 *minor Eximiae devotionis*, Bull No. 4 *minor Eximiae devotionis*.

General Problem Statement and Its Connection with Important Scientific and Practical Tasks.

In this study, we took as a basis the problem statement consisting of searching for and identifying the cause-and-effect relationships between the goals of Christianizing the aborigines of the discovered lands declared by the Apostolic See and the Catholic Monarchs, and the real actions of the local administration of the West Indies from 1492 to 1504.

We compared the originals and translations of original texts in Spanish, English, and Russian, and translated versions from English into Russian. We also used articles by Spanish, American, and other foreign and Russian historians and lawyers written regarding the encomienda [4; 14; 19; 22; 27] and texts from the notes and diaries of Christopher Columbus himself [5].

Practically, this article can be used as a guide when considering the process of the development of the New World by the Crown of Castile and to show the role of Christianization in the abolition of slavery among the Indians and the contradiction with the policy of the local administration of the West Indies.

Novelty:

- Bull No. 4 dated September 26, 1493 (*Bula Dudum siquidem*), received by the Spanish "Catholic Kings," where the Christianization of the Indians was prescribed precisely as a goal, has been translated into Russian;
- The "Decree on the Liberation of Indians Sent by the Admiral as Slaves, June 20, 1500" and parts of the "Will of the Catholic Queen Isabella I of Castile" (1504) have been translated.
- A study of the cause-and-effect relationships was conducted between the declared Christianization of the Indians and a series of changes in laws and the introduction first of elements of the encomienda in 1500 under Francisco de Bobadilla, and then the encomienda itself in 1503 under the Governor of Hispaniola—Nicolás de Ovando.
- The legal weakness of the laws regarding the planned connection between the encomienda and the Christianization of the local population is shown, which was a discrepancy between the practice and theory of Christianization.
- The work is done in a new chronological style, placing the events occurring in their places in space and time.

Object of Study: The object of the study is the history of the political life of the Old World and the New World from 1492 to 1504. **Subject of Study:** The subject of the study is the policy of the Catholic Monarchs, the Holy See, and the local administration of the West Indies.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

Until now, when looking at events in the New World, we use textbooks edited by the Magidoviches [10], I. R. Grigulevich [3; 4], and other authors regarding the purely inhumane treatment of Indians by the Spanish Crown. An example of such views is the article by O. Okuneva [11, pp. 119-120]. Many English-language, French-language, and Russian-language books accused the Spaniards of inhumane treatment of the aborigines of the New World, although the Spanish Crown sought the peaceful Christianization of the population [20].

However, deep studies by Professor E. G. Aleksandrenkov have appeared in Russian science, introducing the encomienda system, and another view of the Conquest by Professor A. F. Kofman, in whose books we saw another side of the Spanish Conquest [1; 7; 8]. Las Casas [4; 9] and Columbus in his letters [6] provide us with important but fragmentary information about Christianization and slavery.

However, this information is insufficient for understanding the cause-and-effect relationships of the policies of the Catholic Monarchs and Columbus toward the aborigines. Therefore, it was necessary to study the "Capitulation of Santa Fe" of 1492 [6], the texts of No. 1 *Breve Inter caetera*, No. 2 *Bula menor Inter caetera II*, No. 3 *Bula menor Eximiae devotionis*, and No. 4 *Bula menor Eximiae devotionis* from 1493 [23], and the text of the will of Isabella I of Castile of 1504 [19; 28]. All this is connected with the events in the West Indies from 1492 to 1504 [14; 19; 27; 22].

Main Body

Attempts to Regulate Relations between Aborigines and Settlers, 1493-1499. When the discovery by Columbus became known in Rome on May 3, 1493, Pope Alexander VI issued a Bull (*Bula No. 1 Breve Inter Caetera*), where Portugal is not even mentioned. The next day—May 4, 1493—the Pope issued a second Bull (*Bula No. 2 Minor Inter Caetera*) [6, p. 615; 19, p. 21; 23, p. 14] which divided the entire known non-Christian world into two parts between Spain (Kingdom of Castile and Leon) and Portugal along a line near the Cape Verde Islands (Literally: "a line drawn and established from the Arctic to the Antarctic poles, whether they find these mainlands and islands in the direction of India or any other side. This line should be a hundred leagues from any of the islands commonly called the Azores and Cape Verde" [6, p. 623; 23, p. 14-18]).

In the Bull (*Bula Inter Caetera of May 3, 1493*), all lands discovered in Columbus's expedition were given forever to the Kings of Castile. Literally: "...we, by the authority of Almighty God granted to us through St. Peter and as vicars of Jesus Christ on earth, give, concede, and assign forever to you and your heirs, the Kings of Castile and Leon [the mentioned lands] with all their dominions, cities, castles, places and villages, with rights, jurisdictions, and all their appurtenances" [6, p. 621].

The lands were given on the condition of the evangelization of the Indians [17, p. 21; 23, p. 12-15], literally: "Among other works pleasing to the Divine Majesty and cherished by our heart, the exaltation of the Catholic faith and Christian religion, and its growth and spread for the salvation of souls and for the humbling and conversion of barbarous nations to the faith itself, holds the highest importance in our time" [6, p. 652].

Thus, upon the discovery of the West Indies, three issues were immediately resolved:

1. On the part of the Catholic Monarchs, there was an economic interest in expanding the borders of the Kingdom of Castile and Leon to new territories to obtain new vassals for Spain, receiving new taxes through payments from a portion of the income from the development of new territories and their subsoil, and increasing income through the economic rise in Spain itself through trade with the new lands.
2. On the part of the Pope and the Catholic Church, there was an interest in expanding the borders of the Christian world to new territories and extending influence over new peoples through their Christianization, with the goal of obtaining income from new Catholic churches.

3. On the part of the Genoese Christopher Columbus, there was an economic interest, multiplied by the guarantees of his lifelong position as Viceroy of the Indies fixed in the "Capitulation of Santa Fe." Literally: "...Your Highnesses appoint the said Don Christopher Columbus as their Viceroy and Governor-General in all the said islands and mainlands that he, as already mentioned, will discover or acquire in the said seas..." [6, p. 150; 23, p. 18].

Now, the Christianization of the aborigines became a mandatory goal as the expansion of the Christian world. On September 25, 1493, Christopher Columbus led the second expedition from Cadiz consisting of 17 ships with 2,500 people. On board, besides settlers and officials, were priests from the Franciscan Order. On September 26, 1493 (the day after Columbus's departure), the Spanish monarchs received Bull No. 4 (*Bula No. 4 Dudum siquidem*), where the division of the world was prescribed and it was stated that for crossing by other countries, their ships "...at their own discretion, may freely detain..." any ships of other states. This Bull was not found in Vatican records and was preserved without a registration mark only in Seville in the General Archive of the Indies (*Archivo de Indias*) [23]. In 1494, Pope Alexander VI, by his Bull, gave the Spanish monarchs Isabella I of Castile and Ferdinand II of Aragon the title of "Catholic Kings" (*Los Reyes Católicos*).

Attempts at Slave Trading, 1495-1499. In March 1495, Christopher Columbus, at the head of 200 Spaniards with horses and dogs, organized the pacification of the rebelling aborigines of the island of Hispaniola. The Indians were subjected to tribute and partially taken into slavery. In 1495, Christopher Columbus personally sent 500 aborigines to Castile to be sold as slaves in Spain, but the Catholic Monarchs did not agree with this decision of Christopher Columbus and released the Indians [27, pp. 200-202]. On April 10, 1495, the royal couple broke off relations with Columbus. Therefore, on June 11, 1496, Columbus returned to Spain to confirm his rights to the discoveries.

In July 1496, in the settlement of Vega Real on Hispaniola, the Indians rebelled once again. Then fever came, and food ran out for the Castilian settlers, who began a revolt against the rule of the Columbuses and against the Indians, whom the rebel settlers killed and turned into slaves. At this time, Christopher Columbus was in Spain and made a proposal to send a third expedition, suggesting to the Spanish kings to recruit criminals for the new campaigns, reducing their sentences by half. The royal couple agreed with Columbus's arguments, as there was a war with France. Based on this, it becomes clear why the settlers who arrived in 1498 were characterized as "...a dissolute rabble, greedy and cruel seekers of profit, who arrived from Castile to the Indies..." [6, p. 961].

On August 31 (August 20), 1498, Christopher Columbus, arriving on Hispaniola, found the island in a state of mutiny. The rebels demanded the distribution of land. In Columbus's letters [6] to the Spanish kings, it is evident that as early as 1498, Columbus planned to get money from the slave trade, which ran counter to the declared goal of Christianization. On October 18, 1498, Christopher Columbus wrote about the slave trade: "...if the information I have is correct, then, as they say, one can sell 4,000 slaves and fetch at least 20 cuento... In Castile, Portugal, Aragon, Italy, and Sicily, on the islands belonging to Portugal and Aragon, and in the Canary Islands, there is a great demand for slaves; and I think they come in insufficient quantities from Guinea.

And the slaves from these lands, if they are brought [to the mentioned countries], will cost three times as much as Guinean ones, as is observed... here there are slaves and dye-wood, which seems a profitable thing, and besides, gold... Now the maestres and sailors are all rich and everyone intends soon to return [to Castile] with a cargo of slaves, and for transport they take 1,500 maravedis per head, not counting the cost of food... And the payment for transport is collected from the very first money received from the sale of slaves. And even if the slaves die on the way—still not all of them face such a fate..." [6, p. 1107].

Columbus sent ships with 600 slaves each, in his words, to try to pay the bills for the expeditions to the Indies. Being in Seville and wishing to look at the ships that had arrived from the West Indies, the Queen of Castile came to the pier and saw the slaves being unloaded [29]. Indignant and outraged by the actions of Christopher Columbus, which he committed contrary to her instructions, Queen Isabella I of Castile uttered the phrase: "What power has my Admiral to give my vassals to anyone?" ("¿Qué poder tiene el mío Almirante para dar a nadie mis vasallos?") [28, pp. 201-202]. Isabella, at her own expense, bought back several surviving Indians from the owners who had purchased them.

Change of Power on Hispaniola and the Arrest of the Columbuses. Prototype of the Encomienda, 1499-1501. On May 21, 1499, the Catholic Kings appointed Francisco Bobadilla—commander of the Order of Alcantara—as judge-governor (*juez-gobernador*) on Hispaniola. This was done in connection with reports arriving in Spain of the rebellion on Hispaniola and the inability of Christopher Columbus and his brother Bartolomé, who was Governor of Hispaniola, to establish administration. Bobadilla was to reorganize the island's management system and brought a royal charter for the distribution of land plots to settlers [6, p. 1107].

On September 28, 1499, 102 rebels received land plots together with Indians attached to the land—this was the first distribution of Indians [11], which later became more official and known as the *encomienda*, and was then called *repartimiento*. This was the first attempt to give land to Castilian settlers and the understanding of the need to develop new laws in the New World. It can be argued that Bobadilla tried to bring some order to the relationship between Spaniards and Indians and the status of Spaniards on the lands in the New World.

On June 20, 1500, Queen Isabella I of Castile promulgated a Decree (*Cedula de 20 de junio de 1500*) to release all found Indians sold up to that moment in Spain and return them for free to Hispaniola on Bobadilla's fleet. And only 13 men and 8 women were found [15, 542]. Literally: "The King and the Queen. Pedro de Torres, Contino... You already know how, in accordance with our mandate, you have in your power the sequestration and have uncovered some Indians who were brought from the Indies and sold in this city and its archbishopric, as well as in other parts of this Andalusia by order of our Admiral of the said Indies, whom we have now ordered to be released, and we have ordered Commander Fray Francisco de Bobadilla to take them with him to the mentioned Indies and fulfill what we have ordered. Therefore, we instruct you that after you give him this certificate of ours and deliver all the named Indians whom you thus have in your power, not missing a single one, by inventory and before a notary, and receive his knowledge of how he receives them from you; which certifies our persons, we order that you no longer be requested or sued..." [15, p. 542].

Francisco Fernández de Bobadilla, upon arrival on August 23, 1500, judged Christopher Columbus in the name of the Kings, and on November 25, 1500, Christopher Columbus and Bartolomé Columbus were brought to Spain to Cadiz in shackles [14; 22]. Thus, slavery for the Indians was abolished in Spain by the aforementioned certificate of June 20, 1500, by Queen Isabella I of Castile [15, p. 48, 542; 19, p. 23], but then allowed only if the Indians were man-eaters (cannibals) by a law issued in 1503, prisoners of war by a law of 1504, or sold by tribes as already being slaves by a law of 1508 [19, p. 23]. After the arrival of the arrested Columbus family in Spain, Queen Isabella released the entire Columbus family in exchange for the renunciation of the rights granted in the New World.

When reading about the events of that time and about the rebellion and customs on Hispaniola, we would like to draw attention to what Christopher Columbus wrote, that "...various opinions are expressed about the possibility of obtaining large revenues: either extracting them by robbery or by developing mines... For a woman here they pay a hundred castellanos, as if for a cultivated field, such is the custom here, many merchants prowl here in search of girls. Nine- and ten-year-olds are in price now. However, one can earn quite a lot on a woman of any age" [6, p. 1136]. This phrase shows the customs prevailing on Hispaniola during the rule of the Columbuses.

Nicolás de Ovando and the Introduction of the Encomienda. 1501-1504. Christianization and the Status of the Aborigines of the New World. Isabella I of Castile's Will. On September 3, 1501, the Catholic Monarchs removed Bobadilla due to poor management and appointed Nicolás de Ovando as Governor of the Indies. Ovando [2, p. 167] was also from the Order of Alcantara and became Governor of the West Indies from 1502 to 1509 [6, p. 1208]. In 1501, by order of Ovando, who was then still in Spain but had already taken office as Governor of Hispaniola, the first slaves of African origin were brought to the island. On February 13, 1502, Nicolás de Ovando set out from Spain for the West Indies with 30 ships and 2,500 Spaniards, including 13 Franciscans [6]. On March 14, 1502, in Valencia, in a letter written by the Catholic Kings to De La Torre, it was noted that the slave trade was prohibited. Literally: "Furthermore, if God wills it and you happen to return, you are obliged to arrive together with our mentioned notary and official, and you must present us with the most complete and detailed report on everything you discover, and on the peoples inhabiting the islands and mainland whom you find. And you must not bring slaves..." [6, p. 1162].

On December 20, 1503, in Spain, in Medina del Campo in the Kingdom of Castile, a Royal Provision was issued [19, p. 21] on the regulation of the work of aborigines. It was written on the basis of the provision given by the Governor-General of the West Indies, Nicolás de Ovando, which he received as a result of a Royal Instruction [19, p. 28-30]. Its scope of compliance, initially limited to Hispaniola and Puerto Rico, subsequently extended to Jamaica and became common for all Spanish territories in the New World. It was Ovando who organized the encomienda system [35]. The essence of this system was well shown by Professor E. G. Aleksandrenkov [1], who provided data on the number of Indians determined for an encomendero depending on status.

The main difference of the encomienda was that it meant a concession not of the land itself as private property, but only of the use of aboriginal labor on that land. Also, the encomienda was given to a settler for merit and could be inherited, but in the case of the encomendero's death, it

passed to the state. The main duty of the king's vassals was the payment of taxes; therefore, the labor of Indians on the encomienda could be used to work to obtain a product—gold, etc.—to obtain profit for the encomendero to pay taxes. Since the Indians were also considered vassals of the Spanish kings, taxes had to be collected from them as well. It turns out that the Spanish settler-encomendero, owning an encomienda to obtain any product for payment, could use the labor of Indians to obtain any product and pay his taxes, and was also responsible for the payment of taxes by the Indians themselves [24, p. 23].

Encomenderos took responsibility for the aborigines living on the land given to them, especially in teaching the Indians the Christian faith, and had to protect the local residents and teach them the Spanish language. Thus, the encomienda imposed on the settler-encomendero guardianship over the aborigines living on the territory of the encomienda. The number of Indians on an encomienda was fixed, and therefore the death of an aborigine gave the owner the opportunity to replenish their number to the amount fixed on paper. This caused the need to send expeditions to neighboring islands to capture Indians as slaves and use them as workers under slave conditions by encomenderos who used the brought Indians instead of the deceased aborigines. The encomienda system, created and introduced by Ovando, became the basic legal model for all overseas territories of the Spanish Crown.

On November 26, 1504, Queen Isabella I of Castile died, leaving a will drawn up on November 23—three days before her death—in which she spoke about the Christianization of the Indians (*Testamento y Codicilo de la Reina Isabel I*) [19, p. 14] [27, pp. 199-203]. Literally: "When the Holy Apostolic See granted us the islands and the mainland of the ocean sea, they were discovered and are to be discovered, as we requested from Pope Alexander VI, of blessed memory, who granted it to us, our principal intention was to try to induce and bring the peoples there and convert them to our holy Catholic faith, and to send prelates, religious figures, clergy, and other learned and God-fearing people to the said islands and Tierra Firme, to instruct their neighbors and inhabitants in the Catholic faith, to teach and instill in them good customs, and to show due diligence in this, according to the letters of the mentioned concession; I very tenderly ask the King, my lord, and command Princess Juana, my daughter, and Prince Philip, her husband, to do this and comply, and this is their principal goal, and to apply great diligence to it, and not to consent to or cause the Indians, neighbors, and inhabitants of these Indies and Tierra Firme, winners or losers, to receive any injury either to their persons or their property, but to command that they be treated well and justly, and if any injury they have received, in nothing should it go beyond what is commanded to us by the apostolic letters of the said concession."

From 1504, the encomienda established itself for several years as the main type of economic management in the New World.

Conclusion

As a result of the study, it was determined that the Papal Bulls were the first legal documents declaring the Indians as future free Christians. Examples are provided that Christopher Columbus repeatedly made attempts at the slave trade, which were condemned by the Catholic Monarchs. Bobadilla's decrees of 1499 on the distribution of land to colonists were the first attempt to establish legal foundations for settlement. In 1503, Nicolás de Ovando introduced the

encomienda, authorized by the Castilian Crown, which made the Spaniards who came to settle in the New World sedentary. This legal structure firmly and for a long time entered the practice of settling new lands in the New World.

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